

Vertiport Placement for Urban Air Mobility to Reduce Time for Multimodal Travel

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Abstract—Urban Air Mobility (UAM) with electric Vertical Take Off and Landing (eVTOL) vehicles can help address ground traffic congestion. Good selection of vertiports (where eVTOLs take off and land) is key for UAM adoption. Existing works on vertiport placement either do not consider UAM as part of a multimodal transportation setup; or do not consider flight trajectories and travel time of eVTOLs. Not considering these factors can result in sub-optimal vertiport placement due to reduced travel time savings.

We complement existing works with VERTIM, a graph-based algorithm for vertiport placement. VERTIM aims to maximize travel time savings from UAM in a multimodal transportation setup. For an accurate and realistic travel time estimation, VERTIM computes time-optimal three-dimensional flight trajectories, while considering a wind field, obstacles, and vehicle battery energy limitations. We evaluate the algorithm with data from New York City for travel to the John F. Kennedy International Airport.

Our experiments show that multimodal taxi+eVTOL commute can improve travel time by up to 40% over a taxi-only ride. VERTIM outperforms a literature-guided baseline by 10.7%. We observe that the flight trajectory; inter-process wait time; battery charge levels; and operational considerations included in trajectory planning; all affect the achievable time savings.

Keywords—Urban Air Mobility; eVTOL; Vertiport placement; 3D trajectory planning; Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Urbanization is an ever-increasing trend globally. By 2050, two out of three people are likely to live in urban areas according to the UN [1]. Such urbanization requires efficient, sustainable, and rapid mass transportation. Because transport infrastructure requires longer term planning and significant capital outlays, it has been unable to keep pace with the rate of urbanization. In the U.S. alone, ground traffic congestion resulted in an annual loss of nearly USD 74B in 2024 due to wasted time and fuel, averaging USD 771 per driver [2]. Urban Air Mobility (UAM) has been proposed as an alternate approach to solving urban ground transport problems by taking advantage of the third dimension. UAM refers to the use of aerial vehicles with short or vertical takeoff and landing capabilities (eVTOLs) for commuting within urban areas. Because eVTOLs can travel at higher speeds and use airspace, they have the potential to significantly augment transport capabilities and therefore, alleviate urban ground congestion. The UAM market is estimated to grow from USD 4.6B in 2024 to USD 23.5B in 2030 [3]. Further, public

acceptance studies [4] have shown a favourable (83%) attitude to UAM and a willingness (71%) to try it.

The creation of the UAM market has led to several companies (e.g., Joby Aviation, Archer Aviation, Volocopter GmbH, The ePlane Co., etc.) focusing on the manufacture and (air-worthiness) certification of eVTOLs. However, adoption of UAM as a viable option of urban transportation requires ground infrastructural requirements to be satisfied and operational challenges to be overcome. First, identifying specialized use-cases (e.g., air ambulances, airport taxis, etc.) with suitable pricing will help in early adoption with hopefully a positive feedback loop. Second, on the ground, we need planning and design of takeoff and landing sites (referred to as ‘vertiports’) and access to and egress from them using other modes of transportation. Finally, in the air, we need air corridors with suitable scheduling and co-existence with existing air traffic. Addressing such challenges is a *sine qua non* for UAM to seamlessly integrate with other urban transportation modes in a multimodal transportation setup and provide time savings in end-to-end travel which can lead to public acceptance [5], [6].

NASA has proposed a 6-level Urban Air Mobility Maturity Scale (UML) for the maturity of UAM operations [7]. The first two levels (UML-1, UML-2) focus on aircraft development, certification, testing, and initial low density, low complexity, low autonomy piloted operations for specific use-cases like carrying passengers to and from commercial airports. In this paper, we address the following question: From the point of view of a city planner or UAM operator, *what are the optimal locations in the city to site vertiports so as to provide end-to-end time savings in a multimodal transportation setup?* Specifically, we focus on UML-2 with the use-case of commuting to a commercial airport as the final destination, as airport transfers are projected to be one of the best use-cases for initial UAM adoption [8]. We use ‘vertiport’ as a general term to refer to any type of pad from (at) which eVTOLs can take off (land) without distinguishing among vertihubs, vertibases, and vertipads [9]. Additionally, we consider a secondary question: *What is the optimal path or trajectory to fly from a given vertiport to the airport in the shortest time while respecting operational considerations?*

A. Related Work

Vertiport placement: Many studies have used Geographic Information System (GIS)-based methods to identify suitable

vertiport locations to meet potential demand for UAM. The modeled demand considers population density, median income, office rent price, places of interest, major transportation nodes, job density, existing travel patterns, and other geographic and socio-economic factors [10], [11]. In Germany, mobility survey data have been used to identify high demand locations for vertiport placement [12]. Specific techniques used include the Analytic Hierarchy Process-Weighted Linear Combination (AHP-WLC)-based suitability analysis [10] and k -means clustering to identify demand clusters [13]. A key limitation of the above studies is that they do not adequately consider multimodal trips; UAM is more likely to be adopted only if vertiports are easily accessible using other modes of transportation.

Some studies consider multimodality and use optimization methods (such as integer programming) to decide vertiport locations. They optimize for the travel cost [14]; total network distance between vertiports and demand points [5]; the total air taxi ridership, the total facility costs, the total travel distances to vertiports [6]; the total revenue generated [8]; or the population-cumulative potential time savings compared to driving [15]. Often, the optimization is modeled as a Hub Location Problem (HLP) where multiple vertiports (i.e., hubs) need to be located to connect different demand points (i.e., trip origins) to the final facility (in our case, airports) [8], [14]. However, as part of the optimization, these studies often simplistically estimate the flight distance or time along the great circle (straight line) path from the origin to the destination. Such a path may not be flyable in reality due to the presence of obstacles, winds, no-fly zones, and other operational constraints along the flight path. Furthermore, they often consider only cruise but not other phases of flight like ascent and descent which occur at speeds lower than cruise. As we show in our experimental evaluation, these simplifications overestimate UAM benefits in a multimodal setup. Thus, we need accurate and realistic flight trajectories for accurate estimates of the flight distance and time.

Trajectory planning: Trajectory planning can be strategic (long term with static, average operational conditions) or tactical (short term with dynamic changes in conditions). In this paper, we focus on strategic planning. Apart from accurate estimates of the flight distance and time, strategic trajectory planning is needed to obtain the eVTOL air corridors.

Due to low altitude flight in dense urban landscapes, an eVTOL trajectory depends on various safety (such as avoiding buildings, terrain, wind gusts, bad weather, other eVTOLs, no-fly restricted areas); social (such as reducing noise pollution, visual pollution, individual privacy infringement); and vehicular (such as maintaining energy efficiency and vehicle performance limits) considerations [16]. It also depends on the wind field prevalent at different locations in the city. A well-planned trajectory reduces the travel time and the energy consumption. In previous studies, trajectory planning for UAM has employed a range of techniques, including optimal control [17]–[19], mixed integer linear programming [20], [21], machine learning [22], and graph-based techniques [23]–[26]. While many of these studies do incorporate vehicular considerations, they often neglect one or more of the

safety, social, or wind field considerations enumerated above. For example, [17] considers the wind field but not the in-path obstacles, whereas [20], [21] incorporate the obstacles but in the absence of any wind. None of the graph-based studies consider the wind field. Thus, a framework which can incorporate most operational considerations including the wind field is needed for trajectory planning.

Graph-based methods have several advantages for trajectory planning. First, the area of consideration can be readily converted into grid points [24] or Voronoi cells [26] that are interconnected to form a graph. Second, operational considerations can be easily encoded along nodes and edges of the graph instead of enumerating them as constraints for integer programming. Third, since trajectory planning usually minimizes a metric defined over a path (for example, total distance, time, cost, or energy), graph-based shortest path algorithms (such as the Dijkstra’s, the Floyd [26], or the Fast-Marching [24] algorithm) can be efficiently applied to get optimal trajectories. Finally, graph-based techniques can be used to obtain the optimal three-dimensional flight trajectory which considers all flight phases, and not just cruise.

B. Our Contributions

We develop a graph-based algorithm called VERTIM (Vertiport placement to Reduce Time for Multimodal travel) to help a city planner or a UAM operator identify optimal locations for placement of vertiports. We demonstrate our algorithm on New York City (NYC) with travel to the John F. Kennedy International Airport (JFK). Our multimodal setup comprises a ground-based taxi from the origin to the vertiport, and an aerial quadrotor eVTOL from the vertiport to JFK. We choose taxis as taxi users are the most prospective UAM users [6]. We aim to maximize the total time savings achievable by taking this multimodal commute compared to a single mode taxi-only commute, for multiple trips from different locations in NYC to JFK.

For realistic flight-time estimation, VERTIM computes the time-optimal three-dimensional flight trajectory from each vertiport to JFK, while considering a wind field; obstacles like buildings, terrain, no-fly zones; and eVTOL battery energy limitations. Our graph-based method encodes various operational considerations as edge weights, and uses the Dijkstra’s Algorithm for computing the time-optimal path. Ours is a planning problem aimed at strategic vertiport placement and trajectory planning for low density UML-2 operations in static operating conditions prevalent in NYC on the average.

Some key findings from our work include the following:

- Areas close to JFK do not benefit from having vertiports and are better off using just a taxi. Areas farther from JFK benefit from UAM in terms of time saved which can be as high as 40% of the taxi-only time to JFK.
- VERTIM results in a more optimal vertiport placement compared to that from criteria based on distance, total taxi time, or geographic and socio-economic factors. The last criterion, which is commonly found in literature, can result in 10.7% lower total time savings than VERTIM.
- The choice of eVTOL flight trajectory is critical to estimating the flight time and therefore, determining the

optimal vertiport locations. Flying along a sub-optimal trajectory can underestimate the best total time savings by as much as 6.3%. Cruising at a lower altitude by avoiding obstacles laterally can be more optimal than cruising along a straighter path at a higher altitude that overflies most obstacles altogether. Flight time can be reduced by harvesting the wind field appropriately.

- A high wait time spent in eVTOL turnaround and other intermediate operations is detrimental to the benefits achievable from UAM. Beyond a wait time of 40 minutes, the time savings become zero.
- The initial and the minimum permissible battery charge levels influence the number and locations of vertiports.
- In-path obstacles like buildings and terrain are more critical to accurate trajectory planning and flight time estimation compared to no-fly POIs or the wind field.

C. Outline

Section II mathematically formulates the vertiport placement optimization problem. Section III describes the datasets needed as inputs to our VERTIM algorithm. Section IV presents the VERTIM algorithm and how it generates the optimal eVTOL flight trajectory while respecting different operational considerations. Section V explains how the optimal trajectory generated in the previous section is used in VERTIM to optimally site vertiports. It also develops various baselines against which we compare VERTIM. Section VI highlights some important results and insights and discusses some limitations of OUR work. Section VII concludes.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We seek to optimize the placement of vertiports in NYC so as to maximize end-to-end travel time savings for a multimodal taxi+eVTOL commute from different areas in NYC to JFK compared to a single mode taxi-only commute. Fig. 1 shows the two travel alternatives.

Let N denote the number of taxi zones in NYC ($N = 263$) from which passengers are picked up by taxis for their commutes to JFK. Fig. 2 shows the different boroughs and taxi zones in NYC. The trip origins (taxi pickups) are assumed to occur at the taxi zone centroids (due to limitations of the NYC taxi trips data as explained in Sec. III). Vertiports, in general, can be located independent of the taxi zones. However, for simplicity, we assume that i) each zone i can have at most one vertiport v_i , and ii) v_i is located at a feasible (i.e., not in a no-fly zone) point closest to the i^{th}

Figure 1: Two mode taxi+eVTOL vs single mode taxi-only commute from pickup point to JFK.

Figure 2: NYC: 5 boroughs, 263 taxi zones, and number of taxi trips to JFK. Image best viewed in color.

zone centroid. We denote by $\delta_i \in \{0, 1\}$ if a vertiport exists in the i^{th} zone ($\delta_i = 1$) or not ($\delta_i = 0$). At the supply side, we assume that any number of eVTOLs are available at any time for trips. At the demand side, we assume that the use of eVTOLs does not induce any additional travel demand.

The saving (Δ_j) in travel time due to the taxi+eVTOL travel from the j^{th} taxi zone over the single mode taxi-only travel is given by

$$\Delta_j := t_{\text{taxi}}(p_j, \text{JFK}) - \min_i \{t_{\text{taxi}}(p_j, v_i) + t_{\text{eVTOL}}(v_i, \text{JFK})\} \quad (1)$$

where, $t_{\text{taxi}}(p_j, v_i)$ is the time taken to travel by taxi from pickup p_j in taxi zone j to a vertiport v_i in taxi zone i , $t_{\text{eVTOL}}(v_i, \text{JFK})$ is the time taken to travel by an eVTOL from a vertiport v_i in taxi zone i to the JFK airport, and $t_{\text{taxi}}(p_j, \text{JFK})$ is the time taken to travel only by taxi from pickup p_j in taxi zone j to the JFK airport. The minimization is over all the vertiport locations i to choose the vertiport which minimizes the total time of travel from zone j to JFK.

For each zone, we define a quantity called the Trip-Time Saving (TTS) as

$$\text{TTS}_j := w_j \Delta_j \quad (2)$$

where, w_j represents the demand for travel from pickup zone j to JFK. Here, we estimate demand simply by the current number of taxi trips. Its distribution across the different zones is shown in Fig. 2. Finally, we define an optimization objective function (O) as

$$O := \sum_{j=1}^N (\mathbb{1}(\Delta_j > 0) \text{TTS}_j). \quad (3)$$

$\mathbb{1}(\Delta_j > 0)$ represents the indicator function which is 1 when $\Delta_j > 0$, else it is 0. Thus, the objective function effectively represents the total time saving across *all* the trips to JFK, which start from only those taxi zones that can give positive time savings for the two mode taxi+eVTOL commute over the single mode taxi-only commute. The optimization problem then is to determine $\delta := \{\delta_i | i = 1 \text{ to } N\}$ (i.e., vertiport locations) such that the objective function (O) is maximized, subject to the constraint that $1 \leq \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i \leq M$, where M

is the maximum number of vertiports allowed (for example, due to budgetary constraints). $t_{\text{taxi}}(p_j, v_i)$, $t_{\text{taxi}}(p_j, \text{JFK})$, and w_j can be estimated from data on taxi trips in the city. To solve the optimization problem, there is need for an accurate estimate of the eVTOL time ($t_{\text{eVTOL}}(v_i, \text{JFK})$), which depends on the eVTOL flight trajectory.

III. DATASETS

We use the following datasets:

- **Taxi Trips and Zones Dataset (TZ):** We obtain data on taxi trips in NYC from the NYC Taxi and Limousine Commission (TLC) Trip Record Database [27]. We use the data to represent the current levels of ground transportation. The dataset contains pickup and dropoff times, locations, trip times, and other fields for trips conducted by the yellow, green, and for-hire taxis. To preserve confidentiality of riders, the trips are mapped to 263 taxi zones in NYC (instead of actual pickup and dropoff coordinates). Thus, we conduct all our analyses at the resolution of these taxi zones and assume that all taxi pickups are from the zone centroids. We gather data containing 22,666,169 trips for one month and average them to get values of the median trip time and number of trips between pairs of taxi zones, and to JFK.
- **Buildings Dataset (BD):** We obtain data on footprint geometries, ground elevations, and roof heights of 1,082,964 buildings in NYC from the NYC OpenData Building Footprints Database [28].
- **Planimetric Dataset (PL):** We obtain data on ground elevation of 387,630 terrain points in NYC from the NYC OpenData Planimetric Database [29].
- **No-Fly POIs Dataset (NF):** We obtain data on 20,643 Points of Interest (POIs) in NYC from the NYC OpenData Points of Interest Database [30]. Out of these, we mark 3,914 POIs categorized as government facilities, military facilities, embassies and consulates, correctional facilities, official landmarks, educational institutions, health services institutions, and zoos as no-fly POIs [31] that we assume cannot be overflowed at any altitude.
- **Wind Dataset (WD):** We obtain data on wind speeds and wind directions for various locations in and around NYC at 10 m and 100 m elevations from the Open-Meteo Historical Weather API [32]. We assume that the wind velocity is steady and has no vertical component.

IV. TRAJECTORY PLANNING

We explain how we generate three-dimensional eVTOL flight trajectories for vertiport placement that satisfy various operational considerations. For simplicity, we assume only three flight phases: i) vertical ascent at a constant speed from the takeoff vertiport to the cruising altitude, ii) level cruise at a constant airspeed at the cruising altitude, and iii) vertical descent at a constant speed from the cruising altitude to JFK.

A. Operational Considerations

We handle the various safety, social, vehicular, and wind field considerations mentioned in Sec. I-A as follows:

- **Separation buffer:** We maintain a lateral and a vertical separation (L) of at least 50 m between the eVTOL and any obstacle like a building, terrain, or a no-fly POI. This separation buffer ensures that safety and social considerations like avoiding collisions, restricted areas, localized wind gusts in the vicinity of buildings; and reducing noise pollution, visual pollution, and privacy infringement for people in buildings and on the ground are automatically respected. It should be noted that L is a parameter in our algorithm and 50 m is just an example distance for demonstration. The algorithm can easily handle any other value of L which may be governed by the eVTOL size and the UAM regulations in place.
- **Wind field:** We use information on wind speeds and directions to calculate the effective ground speed of the eVTOL and its travel time to go from one waypoint to the other. This can help plan trajectories that take advantage of the wind field to effectively increase speed and reduce time of travel.
- **Energy consumption:** We explicitly model the eVTOL battery energy consumption during flight by using a simplified flight dynamics model of the eVTOL. We ensure that the battery charge does not dip below a minimum State of Charge (SOC) threshold, which could lead to unsafe flying conditions. As an example, we assume a minimum SOC threshold (SOC_{\min}) of 0.15.

B. Methodology

We describe our method VERTIM in Algorithm 1. The algorithm starts with various input datasets and parameters. We assume some example values of the parameters just for demonstration in this paper. The algorithm can easily handle other values that may be more realistic when operations commence. The different modules of VERTIM are as follows:

- **CREATEGRID (Line 12 in Algorithm 1):** For each taxi zone, we generate a two dimensional horizontal grid of J points (denoted by λ), which are along and perpendicular to the straight line (great circle) path from the start of cruise (vertically above the origin vertiport; denoted by λ_1) to the end of cruise (vertically above JFK; denoted by λ_j). Each point is at most 20 m (S) away from its immediate neighbor. The grid extends to 1 km (T) on either side of the straight line path. Each taxi zone has its own different grid. We conduct all analyses in the NYC specific NAD83 Cartesian coordinate system and report results in the ellipsoidal WGS84 system. Fig. 3 shows the grid and the NAD83 coordinate axes.
- **GETELEVATION (Line 14):** Using the Buildings (BD) and Planimetric (PL) Datasets, we calculate the maximum elevation Above Mean Sea Level (AMSL) of obstacles in a radius of 50 m (the separation distance (L)) around each grid point, and denote it as ‘MaxEl’. At the origin, the vertiport may be located on the ground or on a building roof. We denote by ‘El₀’ the AMSL elevation of the origin vertiport and by ‘GnEl₀’ the ground elevation at the origin.

Algorithm 1: Algorithm for VERTIM

Inputs:

```

1 TZ, BD, PL, NF, WD // Datasets
2 N = 263 // Number of taxi zones in NYC
3 S = 20 m // Grid resolution
4 T = 1 km // Grid extent
5 ElJFK = 3.96 m // AMSL elevation at JFK
6 L = 50 m // Separation distance
7 SOCinit = 1.0, SOCmin = 0.15 // SOC levels
8 V and eVTOL parameters // Table I
9 Ve = 4 ms-1 // Typical elevator speed
10 twait = 1,200 s // Wait time

```

Trajectory planning:

```

11 for i = 1 to N do // Taxi zones
12   Ji points λi ← CREATEGRID(TZi, S, T)
13   for j = 1 to Ji do // Grid points
14     MaxElij, El0i, GnEl0i ←
15     GETELEVATION(λij, BD, PL, S, L)
16     NoFlyij ← ISNOFLY(λij, NF, L)
17   end for
18   hi ← max(El0i + L, ElJFK + L)
19   for different altitudes h ≥ hi do
20     for j = 1 to Ji do // Grid points
21       Wihj, θihj ← GETWIND(λij, WD, h)
22       βihj ← (h ≥ MaxElij + L) & (~NoFlyij)
23       // ISREACHABLE
24     end for
25     Gih ← CREATEGRAPH(λi, S, h)
26     for each edge eihjk : nihj → nihk in Gih do
27       dihjk ← ||eihjk||2 // Edge length
28       Vg,ihjk ← ||gm law of vector
29       addition(nihj, nihk, Wihj, Wihk, θihj, θihk, V)
30       // Ground speed along edge
31       tihjk ← inf // Edge weight: Time
32       if βihj & βihk then
33         | tihjk ← dihjk/Vg,ihjk
34       end if
35     end for
36   end for
37   tft,ih(h) ← GETFLIGHTTIME(Gih, λ1i, λJi)
38   // Edge Weighted Dijkstra's
39   if SOCfinal < SOCmin then
40     | tft,ih(h) ← inf // CHECKENERGY
41   end if
42 end for

```

Vertiport placement:

```

38 for j = 1 to N do // Pickup zones
39   for i = 1 to N do // Vertiports
40     hbesti ← arg minh(tft,ih(h))
41     teVTOL(vi, JFK) ←
42     (El0i - GnEl0i) / Ve + tft,ih(hbesti) + twait
43     // GETTOTALTIME
44     ttaxi(pj, vi) ← GETTAXITRIPS(TZ, pj, vi)
45   end for
46   ttaxi(pj, JFK), wj ← GETTAXITRIPS(TZ, pj, JFK)
47 end for
48 δ, O ← OPTIMIZE // optimal vertiports

```

Figure 3: Grid points and graph for trajectory planning. The green point represents the start of cruise.

- ISNOFLY (Line 15): For each grid point, using the No-Fly POIs Dataset (NF), we set a Boolean variable 'NoFly' as TRUE if any no-fly POI lies within a radius of $L = 50$ m from the grid point.
- GETWIND (Line 20): Using the Wind Dataset (WD), we estimate for each grid point and altitude, the wind speed W and direction θ (with respect to North, Fig. 3) as the values at the nearest given location in WD, interpolated between the given elevations of 10 m and 100 m.
- ISREACHABLE (Line 21): For each grid point and flight altitude, we denote by a Boolean variable ' β ' whether the point is *reachable*. If the altitude exceeds the maximum elevation of obstacles near the grid point by the separation distance or more, and the grid point does not lie near a no-fly POI, we mark it as reachable ($\beta = \text{TRUE}$).
- CREATEGRAPH (Lines 23–31): For each taxi zone and altitude, we generate a graph G with the grid points as nodes and bidirectional edges between neighboring grid points (as shown in Fig. 3). Bidirectionality is needed due to the wind velocity vector. Each directed edge represents a straight line path from one node to another with respect to the ground. Each edge has a weight which is the time taken to traverse the edge in level cruise, given by the ratio of the edge length to the eVTOL's *ground speed* (V_g) along the directed edge. We compute this ground speed by applying the parallelogram ($\parallel gm$) law of vector addition to the airspeed and the wind velocity vectors ($\vec{V}_g = \vec{V} + \vec{W}$). If either node is not reachable, the time is set to inf as the edge cannot be traversed.
- GETFLIGHTTIME (Line 32): Once all the edge weights in graph G are calculated, we apply the Dijkstra's Algorithm on these edge weights to determine the shortest time path from the start of cruise (λ_1) to the end of cruise (λ_j) and the time for level cruise (t_{cruise}) along this path at a given altitude h . The total eVTOL flight time (t_{ft} ; which is a function of the altitude h) is the sum of the time to vertically ascend from the origin vertiport's elevation El_0 to altitude h , time for level cruise calculated above, and the time to vertically

descend from altitude h to JFK airport's elevation El_{JFK} .

$$t_{\text{ascent}} = \frac{h - El_0}{V_{\text{ascent}}} \quad (4)$$

$$t_{\text{descent}} = \frac{h - El_{\text{JFK}}}{V_{\text{descent}}} \quad (5)$$

$$t_{\text{ft}}(h) = t_{\text{ascent}} + t_{\text{cruise}} + t_{\text{descent}} \quad (6)$$

- **CHECKENERGY** (Lines 33–35): Next, we calculate the battery pack energy consumption (E) and its final SOC at the end of flight ($\text{SOC}_{\text{final}}$) using a simplified eVTOL flight dynamics (Fig. 4) and battery SOC model. We assume the eVTOL to be a quadrotor aircraft as described in [17]. Due to the nature of the grid-graph edges, the flight path is made up of piecewise linear segments along which there is no change in the eVTOL velocity direction. The direction may change from one segment to the other but we do not model the dynamics behind this turning. We assume a constant airspeed and hence, no acceleration in cruise. We also assume a constant air density not varying with altitude. Based on these assumptions, Fig. 4, and the equations in [33], [17], [34], and [35], the flight dynamics for the eVTOL and the evolution of the battery pack SOC are given as:

$$D = 1.1984 \frac{\rho V^2}{2} \quad (7)$$

$$T = \begin{cases} mg + D & \text{in ascent,} \\ \sqrt{m^2 g^2 + D^2} & \text{in cruise,} \\ mg - D & \text{in descent} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$v_h = \sqrt{\frac{T}{2\eta\rho\pi R^2}} \quad (9)$$

$$v_i = \text{Real, positive solution to} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{cases} v_i^2 + Vv_i - v_h^2 = 0 & \text{in ascent,} \\ v_i^4 + 2Vv_i^3 \sin \alpha + V^2 v_i^2 - v_h^4 = 0 & \text{in cruise,} \\ v_i^2 - Vv_i - v_h^2 = 0 & \text{in descent} \end{cases}$$

$$P_{\text{ascent}} = \kappa T v_i + TV + 0.125 \rho \pi \Omega^3 R^5 \sigma C_d F_p \quad (11)$$

$$P_{\text{cruise}} = \kappa T v_i + DV + 0.125 \rho \pi \Omega^3 R^5 \sigma C_d F_p \quad (12)$$

$$P_{\text{descent}} = \kappa T v_i - TV + 0.125 \rho \pi \Omega^3 R^5 \sigma C_d F_p \quad (13)$$

$$E = \sum_{k \in \{\text{ascent, cruise, descent}\}} P_k t_k \quad (14)$$

$$\text{SOC}_{\text{final}} = \text{SOC}_{\text{init}} - \frac{E}{E_{\text{batt.,max.}}} \quad (15)$$

Here, D is the vehicle drag, T is the total thrust produced by all the rotors, v_h is the rotor hover induced velocity, v_i is the rotor induced velocity¹, α is the angle of attack of the rotor plane in level cruise ($T \cos \alpha = mg$, $T \sin \alpha = D$), P is the power required in different phases of flight (which should not be more than the maximum power deliverable $P_{\text{max.}}$), t is the time of flight in different phases, and SOC_{init} is the initial battery SOC that we assume to be 1 unless otherwise mentioned. Other parameters and their values are given in Tab. I.

¹Equation (10) in descent is only applicable for small magnitudes of descent speed for which $V \leq 0.2v_h$ [33] (like the 1.5 ms^{-1} in our work).

Figure 4: Simplified model of eVTOL dynamics. Velocity vectors are in the direction of the air as seen by the vehicle.

TABLE I. eVTOL parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Ref.
Air density	ρ	1.225 kgm^{-3}	ISA
Airspeed	V	Ascent: 1.5 ms^{-1} Cruise: 50.4 ms^{-1} Descent: 1.5 ms^{-1}	[36] [17] [36]
Vehicle mass	m	2,940 kg	[17]
Acc. due to gravity	g	9.8 ms^{-2}	
Number of rotors	η	4	[17]
Rotor radius	R	4 m	[17]
Induced power factor	κ	1.75	[17]
Rotor speed	Ω	$30.12 \text{ rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	[17]
Rotor solidity ratio	σ	0.055	[17]
Rotor mean blade drag coefficient	C_d	0.0089	[17]
Profile power factor	F_p	0.97	[17]
Max. power	$P_{\text{max.}}$	494.25 kW	[17]
Max. battery energy	$E_{\text{batt.,max.}}$	1,331 MJ	[35]

We assume that all the rotors are identical in terms of performance. We also assume battery efficiency to be 1 for simplicity. We can see that the power required in each phase is a constant and therefore, the energy required in each phase is directly proportional to the time of flight in that phase. If $\text{SOC}_{\text{final}} \geq \text{SOC}_{\text{min}}$, then the trajectory is feasible from an energy perspective, with t_{ft} as that given by (6). Otherwise, no trajectory is feasible at the given altitude and we set t_{ft} to inf at that altitude.

V. VERTIPOINT PLACEMENT OPTIMIZATION

Once the flight trajectory and flight time have been computed for each taxi zone and altitude, we can solve the optimization problem of vertiport placement formulated in Sec. II. We also describe some comparative baselines.

A. Methodology

We add three more modules to Algorithm 1 as follows:

- **GETTOTALTIME** (Lines 40–41): For each taxi zone, we first determine the best altitude h_{best} that minimizes the flight time $t_{\text{ft}}(h)$ from that zone to JFK. This best altitude determines the optimal air corridor for flying from a vertiport in that zone to JFK. Apart from the actual flight time, the eVTOL leg of the commute will also spend extra time in i) ascending from the ground to the roof if the origin vertiport is located on the top of a building, and ii) operations like passenger check-in, security checks, boarding, eVTOL battery recharging, startup, phase of flight transition, eVTOL turn off, passenger deboarding, and other unaccounted time leakages. We estimate the

former by dividing the height of the origin vertiport building by a typical elevator ascent speed (V_e) of 4 ms^{-1} [37]. We call the latter as waiting time (t_{wait}) and assume it to be 20 minutes (for demonstration), unless otherwise mentioned. Thus, the total time required for the eVTOL leg of the trip from vertiport v to JFK (that appears in (1)) is

$$t_{\text{eVTOL}}(v, \text{JFK}) = \frac{E_{l_0} - G_n E_{l_0}}{V_e} + t_{\text{ft}}(h_{\text{best}}) + t_{\text{wait}}. \quad (16)$$

- **GETTAXITRIPS** (Lines 42, 44): We use the Taxi Trips and Zones Dataset (TZ) to calculate the median time taken by a taxi to travel from a pickup zone p to a vertiport v ($t_{\text{taxi}}(p, v)$), and to travel from a pickup zone p to JFK ($t_{\text{taxi}}(p, \text{JFK})$). We also determine the current number of taxi trips from a taxi zone p to JFK (w).
- **OPTIMIZE** (Line 46): The final module is responsible for determining the optimal vertiport locations to maximize the total Trip-Time Saving objective (O) in (3). We use the constraint programming solver `cp-sat` from the Google `or-tools` optimization suite [38] in `Python` for optimization; with the formulation described in Sec. II. We do all analyses on a desktop-class machine.

B. Baselines

In this section, we describe some baseline approaches for comparison with VERTIM. Each baseline uses either i) one or more simple criteria for vertiport placement, ii) prior studies in literature, or iii) alternative trajectories.

- **BL1: Distance criterion:** This method uses distance from JFK as the sole criterion to place a vertiport. Taxi zones that are farther from JFK will get vertiports first.
- **BL2: Total taxi time criterion:** This method uses the number of taxi trips multiplied by the median taxi time from a taxi zone to JFK ($w_j t_{\text{taxi}}(p_j, \text{JFK})$ in (1)–(3)) as the criterion to place a vertiport. Taxi zones that have a higher value of this quantity (thus, representing more travel time over all trips) will get vertiports first.
- **BL3: Multi-criteria decision making considered in literature:** As mentioned in Sec. I-A, many studies have used Geographic Information System (GIS)-based methods that use multiple geographic and socio-economic criteria to decide vertiport locations [39]. One such method is Analytic Hierarchy Process-Weighted Linear Combination (AHP-WLC)-based suitability analysis [10] that we use as a baseline. This method enables the integration of heterogeneous geospatial and socio-economic data into a structured, quantifiable decision-support model. First, we consider four key categories of factors: transportation and connectivity, socio-economic factors, areas of attraction, and safety and infrastructure readiness. We select the categories based on their relevance to UAM operations. We then gather and analyze data relevant to these categories, such as the distribution of population, income, EV charging stations, fire stations, places of interest (hospitals, schools, commercial hubs), and transportation nodes (bus stops, taxi trips, and subway stations) across the different NYC taxi zones. For each

category, we normalize the data values using max-normalization to maintain comparability across scales. We then assign relative importances to the factors in a category and construct pairwise comparison matrices. Using these matrices, the AHP framework then yields a set of category-specific weights through eigenanalysis. We apply these weights to the normalized data values to compute an intermediate score for each category. We compute the final composite suitability index for each taxi zone by aggregating the four category scores using an unweighted arithmetic mean assuming equal importance across categories - an assumption made to ensure baseline neutrality in the absence of stakeholder-driven prioritization. This index represents the relative suitability of each taxi zone for initial vertiport placement. Taxi zones that have a higher value of this index will get vertiports first.

- **BL4: Highest building altitude trajectory:** We use the optimal air corridor (at the best altitude) for each taxi zone to calculate the total time needed for the eVTOL leg of the commute (16) for VERTIM as well as baselines BL1, BL2, and BL3. To quantify the benefit of this optimal trajectory in deciding vertiports, like in [21], we use an alternate trajectory that ascends to clear the tallest building or terrain along the great circle path. We determine the shortest path to cruise at that altitude given the wind condition and the no-fly zone constraints (as buildings/terrain would not be obstacles). We use this trajectory to calculate the total flight time and then determine the vertiport locations in BL4.
- **BL5: Lowest cruise time trajectory** Here, we choose a trajectory that minimizes only the cruise time and does not consider the ascent and descent times for optimization. We use this trajectory to calculate the total flight time and then determine the vertiport locations.

VI. RESULTS

In this section, we highlight some key results and insights from our method VERTIM and compare it with the developed baselines. We also discuss some limitations of our work.

A. Number of Vertiports and Their Locations

Fig. 5a shows how the total TTS optimization objective (O in (3)) changes with the maximum number of vertiports allowed (M). As expected, the total TTS increases with M . More end-to-end time benefits can be achieved for a taxi+eVTOL commute over a taxi-only commute with more vertiports. We see that the curve starts to plateau about $M = 50$. Hence, for all further analyses, we choose 50 as the *maximum* number of vertiports allowed. Unless specifically mentioned otherwise, this $M = 50$ also results in 50 as the *actual* number of optimal vertiports.

Figs. 5b and 5c show the locations of the 50 optimal vertiports and their impact on pickups from different taxi zones, colored by the trip-time saving (TTS in (2)) and the time saving (Δ in (1)), respectively. The taxi zones marked by a black boundary indicate the zones which have a vertiport. We see that most of the vertiports are located in the boroughs

Figure 5: Number, location, and impact of vertiports by VERTIM. Image best viewed in color.

of Manhattan (25/50) and Brooklyn (18/50), with only a few in Queens (3/50), Bronx (2/50), and Staten Island (2/50). The presence of vertiports in Staten Island is especially beneficial as it will increase connectivity from the island to the rest of NYC. Pickups from zones which are colored in yellow-green benefit from a taxi+eVTOL commute compared to a taxi-only commute ($TTS > 0$ in Fig. 5b and $\Delta > 0$ in Fig. 5c). Those colored in grey do not. Large swathes, particularly in Queens, are better off using just a taxi. Areas farther from JFK, particularly in Manhattan and Brooklyn, derive benefit from UAM in terms of travel demand and time saved. The time saved can be as high as 30 minutes (40% of the taxi-only time to JFK) per trip for pickups in some zones, despite the wait time (t_{wait}) of 20 minutes assumed. An interesting observation is that the geometric city center may not have any vertiport, due to how the number of taxi trips and trip times are spatially distributed in NYC; and how the eVTOL and taxi speeds compare with each other.

B. Comparison with Baselines

Fig. 6 shows that VERTIM gives a higher total TTS than all other baselines, for every value of M . Thus, merely using criteria based on distance, total taxi time, or socioeconomic factors are inadequate for vertiport placement to

Figure 6: Comparison of VERTIM with different baselines. Image best viewed in color.

reduce the end-to-end multimodal travel time. The distance-based baseline BL1 gives the worst performance. BL1, BL2, and BL3 give a 90%, 5.4%, and 10.7% lower total TTS than VERTIM, respectively, for $M = 50$. This underestimation of TTS translates to a sub-optimal placement of vertiports.

Comparison of VERTIM with baselines BL4 and BL5 shows that a sub-optimal eVTOL trajectory can underestimate the best total TTS achievable, by as much as 6.3% for 50 vertiports. The sub-optimality of BL4 shows that cruising at a lower altitude by avoiding obstacles laterally (as in VERTIM) is better than cruising along a straighter path at a higher altitude that overflies most obstacles altogether (as in BL4). The sub-optimality of BL5 shows the importance of all flight phases, including ascent and descent, and not just cruise.

C. Optimal Flight Trajectory

Fig. 7 shows the characteristics of the optimal flight trajectory from an example vertiport in Manhattan to JFK. The vertiport is 19.7 km from JFK. VERTIM places this vertiport on the roof of a building that is 22 m above the ground. The best cruising altitude chosen is 109 m AMSL. Fig. 7a shows the horizontal distance and the vertical altitude profiles in all the three flight phases as seen from the ground. The distance profile shows that the average ground speed in cruise is 49.2 ms^{-1} (177 km/h), faster than any mode of ground transportation. The flight time is 9.2 minutes, and the total time (including wait time) for the taxi+eVTOL commute from this zone to JFK is 34.8 minutes on an average. On the contrary, a taxi-only commute needs a median of 45.2 minutes. UAM achieves an end-to-end time saving of about 23%. Starting with an SOC of 1, the SOC at trip end is 0.9, which allows future trips without recharging.

The inset in Fig. 7b shows the optimal cruise trajectory on the map of NYC. The main part of Fig. 7b shows its zoomed in view near the start of cruise along with the straight line great circle path for comparison. It also shows the grid used in VERTIM; the obstacle buildings and the no-fly POIs; and the static wind field at the altitude of 109 m. The great circle path passes through many buildings and no-fly POIs making it infeasible for flight. However, the optimal path by VERTIM navigates around all the obstacles maintaining a safe separation distance from them. Moreover, the planned optimal path is laterally shifted in the direction of the wind

(a) Horizontal distance and altitude vs. time.

(b) Top view of cruise trajectory (inset) and its zoomed in view.

Figure 7: Optimal trajectory from a vertiport in Manhattan to JFK at a cruising altitude of 109 m. Image best viewed in color.

so as to take advantage of a tailwind at the start of cruise. Due to this tailwind, the ground speed at the start of cruise is 55.1 ms^{-1} (198 km/h) which exceeds the airspeed of 50.4 ms^{-1} (181 km/h) by 9%. Thus, VERTIM handles all the realistic operational considerations encountered in eVTOL flight.

D. Effect of Wait Time

Fig. 8 shows the effect of the wait time (t_{wait}) on the output of VERTIM for $M = 50$ vertiports. As the wait time increases, the total trip-time saving reduces thereby indicating that a higher wait time is detrimental to the benefits achievable by using taxi+eVTOL over taxi alone. Beyond a wait time of 40 minutes, the benefits become zero. Moreover, as the wait time increases, only pickups from fewer taxi zones located farther from the airport benefit from UAM. Therefore, it is important to improve efficiency of eVTOL turnaround and other intermediate operations so that the wait time can be reduced and the benefits from UAM can be maximized.

Figure 8: Effect of wait time on VERTIM output.

E. Effect of Battery Pack Initial SOC

Fig. 9 shows the effect of the initial eVTOL battery pack SOC (SOC_{init}) for $M = 50$ vertiports. For clarity, the three curves are not shown beyond an initial SOC of 0.3 as they plateau out. As the initial SOC reduces, the final SOC ($\text{SOC}_{\text{final}}$) at the end of the journey also reduces. For initial $\text{SOC} \geq 0.25$, 50 optimal vertiports are feasible as the final

Figure 9: Effect of initial SOC on VERTIM output.

$\text{SOC} \geq 0.15$ (SOC_{min}) for a trip starting from any of these vertiports. As the initial SOC ranges between 0.25 and 0.2, fewer vertiports remain feasible in ensuring a final SOC of 0.15. These vertiports offer diminishing returns in TTS as they are located closer to JFK. When initial $\text{SOC} \leq 0.2$, no vertiports are feasible to ensure a sufficient final SOC at JFK.

F. Ablation Study of Operational Considerations

It may not always be possible to incorporate operational considerations like buildings and terrain obstacles (bt), no-fly POIs (nf), and the wind field (wd) when planning vertiport locations and eVTOL flight trajectories in a city. This could be due to a lack of good quality geospatial or weather data for the city. To understand the effect of neglecting these different factors, we conduct an ablation study that neglects one or more of these three operational considerations. Neglecting a consideration overestimates the total trip-time saving compared to the real-world case that includes all the considerations. This overestimation can lead to a sub-optimal placement of vertiports not reflective of real-world operations. Fig. 10 shows the percentage overestimation in the total TTS for different scenarios compared to the real-world case as a function of M . Neglecting the wind ($\text{wd} = \text{N}$; red curve) or the no-fly POIs ($\text{nf} = \text{N}$; blue curve) can overestimate the total TTS by 1.9–2.6% for values of M exceeding 50. Neglecting buildings and terrain obstacles ($\text{bt} = \text{N}$; green

Figure 10: Effect of ablation study on total TTS (Y = Yes, N = No).

curve) can lead to an even higher overestimation error of 13.1–16.2%, which indicates that such obstacles are more crucial to trajectory planning, time estimation, and vertiport placement compared to no-fly POIs or the wind field. Lastly, neglecting all the three considerations (purple curve), which results in the eVTOL cruising along the great circle path at the minimum permissible altitude, can overestimate the total trip-time saving by as much as 20%.

G. Limitations

We highlight some limitations of our work arising out of the different assumptions made. First, we have only considered the particular use-case of traveling to the airport and have not considered travel between any two arbitrary locations. Second, we have modeled current travel demand by only the taxi trips, and have not considered other modes of ground transportation (like buses and subway) or other geographic and socio-economic factors that influence demand in our optimization. Third, we have not included realistic limits imposed by fleet availability, throughput, and scheduling. Fourth, we have not considered phases of flight like taxi, hover, and smooth transition between cruise and ascent/descent. Finally, our flight dynamics and battery energy models do not consider accelerating or turning flight, or any performance limits on various vehicle and battery parameters.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We develop a graph-based algorithm called VERTIM to identify optimal locations for vertiports in a city. The objective is to maximize travel time savings from UAM in a multimodal transportation setup. For an accurate and realistic travel time estimation, VERTIM computes time-optimal three-dimensional flight trajectories, while considering a wind field; obstacles like buildings, terrain, no-fly zones; and vehicle battery energy limitations. We observe that the time saving by using a taxi+eVTOL commute can be as high as 40% of the taxi-only time. More importantly, not all areas in a city would reduce travel time using UAM. This underscores the importance of careful vertiport placement. VERTIM outperforms various baselines that use simpler criteria or prior

studies in literature for vertiport placement. By extensive comparative studies, we demonstrated that the choice of the eVTOL flight trajectory, the inter-process wait time, the battery charge levels, and the operational considerations affect the time savings achievable from UAM. At a minimum, the buildings and terrain in a city that can obstruct eVTOL flight should be considered in trajectory planning and vertiport placement.

Future directions to our work could aim to address some limitations identified earlier. Specifically, they could include: i) a rigorous UAM-demand modeling based on various geographic and socio-economic factors, ii) exploring other use-cases for UAM apart from airport commute, iii) incorporating more flight phases, iv) solving challenges arising from fleet availability, throughput, scheduling limitations; and resource (for example, number of take-off/landing pads and number of charging stations at each vertiport) bottlenecks, v) using a better flight dynamics and battery energy model in the presence of performance limits to give realistically flyable trajectories that do not inconvenience passengers, and vi) re-planning of trajectories in the presence of multiple eVTOLs with inter-eVTOL separation constraints, and dynamically changing operational conditions.

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